

The Language Act

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Abstract

The link between language and culture is the society. When it is been mentioned about social life it depends actually on the language spoken between the people. Here language is the communication aspect to the gap between cultures. There is a great depend on the linkage capacity which language make between nations with different tongues. Here the aspect is confidential because the gap scrutinized to duel across the given role of language. There is a handful trial to improve the decrease of this gap in what is called tourism. In all the world the looking for other places and cultures make it a sensed variety to ignore the differences between different roots. There is a heartfull suggestions to realize the great intonation for the real formation of the levels of people and the recent generations attitudes towards language. There is an inheritance of capacity for different groups give us an encourage to rectify the objects to be dealt with in other usage of language in many cases or many critical opinions about one language usage in all the world with the great influence of English Language.

Introduction

The respectful characters in all the world can be said for example Kings or Presidents thus they stick to speak their own languages in the world wide meetings. This give the different languages an encouragement to be known around all the world.

Naw adays the development of the world technology as is been said always make it easy to learn another language(s). At the circumstances of multilingual ability is common in all the world recently.

So let the topic be back to the language act. In an act of language it has been leading to be spoken about society and social life as one of the scholars has spoken social context and social factors. Ellis(1994)

It has been spoken that social context has different settings. They are natural which is informal and educational which is formal. For the social factors they are as follows age, sex, social class and ethnic identity. These influence language outcomes. It can be said about language context and language function. When language context is mentioned then can be asked whether the alphabet of the language can be learnt easily? Or it's grammar can be studied easily? The things which this language contained so as to be learnt and studied easily.

The function for example many questions can be asked like: why do people need to study this language? How can it be studied? In which situation? In what ways it can be learnt? Who will teach it? Who will study it and why? What can be studied? Where can it be studied? All these questions to understand the factors behind studying this special language not just the functions.

When considering context of language settings one of them is natural setting, which is informal. A baby he/she imitate his parents or relatives in trying to speak. This a native speaker features and definitions and it is not the scope. The hint is the adult learner of a language. He/she try to learn from neighbours (in the target language country), market, transportation and colleagues. Those are the natural way to learn a language or languages. It can be any where around the world.

In special countries throughout villages people learn each other languages by contacting in that natural way. And the one can find himself or herself speaking several languages. This is called multilingualism. Finding the truth about this in India, Africa Southern America. There can be a lot of multilingual people, who learn language naturally or much more linguistically informally.

Recently students and other adult people also can learn through the internet sometimes classes can be informal with the net. Learning or chatting with a person in WhatsApp some people can learn like this it is informal. Watching TV in other language a person can learn it is also informal setting or natural setting. From songs a person can learn also words here and there from any language. From internet it can be named natural learning, because it is in one's pocket(a mobile) at one's shoulder (a lab top). So this is the thing in general.

Unless it is special classes a person has a teacher so this called formal setting or what is called educational setting. This is can be in the internet or institutions different kind of classes. Following proper teaching for example classes of grammar or listening and speaking, classes of writing other classes of reading. And this the way in learning a language. Different aspects of learning and teaching all around the world. Recent time people

beside their different specializations they try to learn a new language, because it has a special role in their specialty.

Some reflections of factors setting of learning a language, the first factor is age. Scholars tried to control this but under any title in linguistics it can be seen the importance of speaking about age as a critical factor with its critical periods childhood, teenagers and adults (different standardization in this). When it is handed like this the importance of age can be recognized as a degradation aspect. Following what is said about childhood books is written about it not just theories. The critical period from age three till eleven, after it the adolescence period then adulthood. Young adults from eighteen till twenty nine also a period that to be under a microscope, because it is time the student link with a university and try to have a job to lead his/her life. Elder than twenty nine this lead to life leading working, learning, marrying and bringing children for the stabilization of the race of Human Beings. When it is spoken about to learn a language it can be any where in that leveling the age of people.

So far so good to establish the design of mind to recruit the importance of time to ask how old is she or he? Does she or he has time to learn other language and why? When circumstances are established it will be needed views around the world to recognize the younger the person the faster the learning will be. This in general special opinion.

The other factor less important than age us sex. Whether a male or a female is speaking or learning. In linguistics there is great consideration about the type of human being who is going to learn or speak, let it be generalized the person who is contacting people. The special thing here when it is spoken about sex a male or female to learn, all the factors come together age, sex, social group and ethnic identity. Because here it have to be mentioned the following:-

What is the learners' (he/she) age?

Is the learner (he/she)going to education(and till what age)?

What is the learner social class?

What is the learner ethnic identity?

These are an auditory marks because this is life. There are group of people in different parts of the world, who have an opinion in education for girls. They don't let the girls to schools and even if they let them to certain age then here stop and go to marriage. The same situation for boys, if they go to education till certain age after that to work. So life and circumstances are different for each group of people in the world. Let alone to study other language or languages.

When it has been spoken about language act for sure it has to be spoken about speech act , here are some extracts from the internet:-

*In linguistics, a **speech act** is an utterance defined in terms of a speaker's intention and the effect it has on a listener. Essentially, it is the action that the speaker hopes to provoke in his or her audience. Speech acts might be requests, warnings, promises, apologies, greetings, or any number of declarations. (1)*

Speech-Act Theory (2)

Speech-act theory is a subfield of pragmatics. This area of study is concerned with the ways in which words can be used not only to present information but also to carry out actions. It is used in linguistics, philosophy, psychology, legal and literary theories, and even the development of artificial intelligence.

Speech-act theory was introduced in 1975 by Oxford philosopher J.L. Austin in "How to Do Things With Words" and further developed by American philosopher J.R. Searle. It considers three levels or components of utterances: locutionary acts (the making of a meaningful statement, saying something that a hearer understands), illocutionary acts (saying something with a purpose, such as to inform), and perlocutionary acts (saying something that causes someone to act). Illocutionary speech acts can also be broken down into different families, grouped together by their intent of usage.

Locutionary, Illocutionary, and Perlocutionary Acts

To determine which way a speech act is to be interpreted, one must first determine the type of act being performed. Locutionary acts are, according to Susana Nuccetelli and Gary Seay's "Philosophy of Language: The Central Topics," "the mere act of producing some linguistic sounds or marks with a certain meaning and reference." So this is merely an umbrella term, as illocutionary and perlocutionary acts can occur simultaneously when locution of a statement happens.

Illocutionary acts, then, carry a directive for the audience. It might be a promise, an order, an apology, or an expression of thanks—or merely an answer to a question, to inform the other person in the conversation. These express a certain attitude and carry with their statements a certain illocutionary force, which can be broken into families.

Perlocutionary acts, on the other hand, bring about a consequence to the audience. They have an effect on the hearer, in feelings, thoughts, or actions, for example, changing someone's mind. Unlike illocutionary acts, perlocutionary acts can project a sense of fear into the audience.

Take for instance the perlocutionary act of saying, "I will not be your friend." Here, the impending loss of friendship is an illocutionary act, while the effect of frightening the friend into compliance is a perlocutionary act.

The conception of language as a means of action has become a topic of sustained investigation by philosophers of language and linguists within the theory of speech acts. The pursuit of this approach is to examine such bits by considering them communicative units. The present paper elucidates the foundations of this pragmatic theory as formulated by its leading figures Austin and Searle and goes even further to explain how the original speech act conceptualization is connected to research in the field of discourse analysis and how it was transferred to the description of written discourse. (3)

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